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3 Measurement properties of wearable kinematic-based data collection systems to evaluate ball kicking in soccer: a systematic review with evidence gap map

1 Abstract: Kinematic assessment of ball kicking may requires significant human effort (e.g., traditional vision-based tracking systems). Wearables offer a potential solution to reduce processing time. This systematic review collated measurement properties (validity, reliability, and/or accuracy) of wearable kinematic-based technology systems used to evaluate soccer kicking. Seven databases were searched for studies published on or before April, 2024. The protocol was previously published and followed the PRISMA 2020 statement. The data items included any validity, reliability and/or accuracy measurements extracted from the selected articles. Twelve articles (1011 participants) were included in the qualitative synthesis, showing generally (92%) moderate methodological quality. The authors claimed validity (e.g., concurrent) of in 7 of 8 studies found on the topic, reliability in 2 of 3, and accuracy (event detection) in 3 of 3 studies. The synthesis method indicated moderate evidence on concurrent validity of MPU-9150/ICM-20649 InvenSense and PlayerMaker™ devices. However, limited-to-no evidence was identified across studies when considering wearable devices/systems, measurement properties and specific outcome variables. To conclude, there is a knowledge base that may support the implementation of wearables to assess ball kicking in soccer practice while future research should further evaluate the measurement properties to attempt to reach a strong evidence level.

Keywords: Sports engineering; Quality control; Measurement error; Technique; Football; Human movement; Validity; Reliability; Accuracy; Performance analysis.

1. Introduction

In the sports engineering field, particularly in the context of team ball sports, one of the main goals is to conceive monitoring tools that can be used in naturally occurring environments [1,2]. This is given the general poor construct validity of laboratory or even field-based tests outside game-play to evaluate skill-related performance, such as in the case of soccer kicking (i.e. passing or shooting) ability [3–6]. Testing and reporting the soccer kicking skill features (e.g. lower limb movement pattern and velocity) to coaching staff is of paramount importance since (a) it could help provide feedback aiming at perfecting players' movements [1], (b) there are strong relationships between kicker mechanical parameters and kick outcomes [7–10] and (c) it is not negligible the number of injury occurrences (e.g., >10–15%) associated to ball kicking events [11–13] which in turn may be prevented with adequate monitoring of player motions under training or match conditions. In this sense, wearable technologies has been recognized to assist in biofeedback purposes [14]. Indeed, both are frequent in soccer contexts, the use/perception of the importance of wearables and monitoring of key performance indicators derived from ball kicking features (e.g., shooting or passing metrics) [15,16].

To collect data on position, velocity and acceleration during kicking movement, there are various electronic performance and tracking systems (EPTS) currently commercially available, such as optical-based, inertial measurement units (IMUs), GNSS, and LPS [17–19]. High-speed semi-automatic 3-dimensional optical systems are generally considered the “gold standard” given their lowest levels of reported

measurement error [18,20]. However, these systems are limited in capture volumes and traditionally require reflective markers attached to players' bodies [17] and can also be labor-intensive. Consequently, the use of this method during official competition is therefore limited. In this sense, artificial intelligence-assisted markerless video-based tracking could be a possible solution, representing a less invasive method for capturing kicking data [1,21]. Aside from the advantages of such a straightforward approach, calibration of extended volumes is challenging, potential occlusion effects can still occur, and it is necessary to position the cameras in optimal locations (e.g., high). Once again, this can collectively constrain the use of optical-based systems when investigating in-game ball kicking in soccer.

22 Since the mid-2010s, the Fédération Internationale de Football Association (FIFA) has allowed the use of EPTS [22]. Although biofeedback appears to be available in various of the current EPTS, its definitive implementation in day-to-day practice has not yet been widely observed, as in the case of soccer kick testing/monitoring [23]. IMUs (e.g., Xsens Technologies B.V., the Netherlands) represent a wearable type of EPTS that may allow kicking kinematics to be obtained [24]. In fact, wearables may assist in overcoming various of the limitations mentioned above associated with the use of video-based techniques, also helping in possibly providing real-time data [25]. On the other hand, not all of them are feasible to apply in competition settings. Examples included those multi-sensor apparatus requiring unique clothing and/or reinforced attachment on various body locations, which may potentially constrain movement patterns. Starting from September 2023, a specific wearable foot-mounted apparatus that enables tracking lower extremity movements was the first of the category

approved by FIFA, the so-called "PLAYERMAKER" system (Playermaker LTD) [26,27].

Of note is that there are recent criticisms regarding some aspects of FIFA quality performance reports for EPTS [28,29].

While several previous literature reviews addressed methodological details of wearables applied to kinematic analysis in sports tasks [25,30–39], none have solely examined soccer kicking skill. Thus, it is still lacking a systematic analysis of the level of scientific evidence available as concerning the specific measurement properties of wearables used in monitoring ball kicking actions. One particular concern when assessing soccer kicking movement kinematics refers to the potential distortion on time-series data caused by the impact of the foot with the ball [40,41]. Also, ball kicking may involve a very rapid change in speed values of the lower extremity from preparation until follow through. The concomitant demands upon velocity and accuracy constraints, which are known to elicit paradoxical central inputs of players [42], probably tend to contribute to producing a substantial degree of variability in the assessment of soccer kicking as well [43]. This emphasizes the need to choose the methods for collecting/processing kick data carefully. Taken together, there is an evident necessity to collate studies that have determined measurement errors of wearable technology devices used to measure biomechanical aspects of soccer kicking as this can help inform practitioners, researchers and industry workers in the area. Therefore, the present study aims to synthesize evidence from scientific journal articles that provided data about measurement properties (validity, reliability, and/or accuracy) of wearable kinematic-based technology systems used to evaluate ball kicking in the soccer context, through a systematic literature review.

7 2. Methods

The protocol established for the present systematic review was previously registered (OSF REGISTRIES – project ZM3J6) and has been available in full elsewhere [44].

The Institutional Research Ethics Committee from the Universidad César Vallejo Perú, granted permission to run the review study. The review protocol was established considering the items from the PRISMA 2020 statement [45].

2.1. Database searches

10 Table 1 contains terms used for the searches across the databases selected. For the formulation of the search string, terms between the same column were combined with the Boolean operator OR, while the groups of terms between columns were combined with the Boolean operator AND. The searches were performed on April 23, 2024,

2 through seven electronic databases: EBSCOHost, IEEE Xplore, Physical Therapy and Sports Medicine, ProQuest, PubMed, Scopus and Web of Science.

Table 1. Search terms used for the current systematic review through a PICO

framework. *Wildcard term.

Population

Intervention

Comparison

Outcome

soccer

wearable*

validity

kick*

football*

inertial measurement unit

reliability

shoot*

association football

IMU

measurement error

pass*

11-a-side

acceleromet*

accuracy

skill

microtechnology

precision

technical

1 micro-electrical mechanical system

MEMS

global positioning system

global navigation satellite system

1 local positioning system

GPS

GNSS

LPS

1 The selected search terms attempted to respect the PICO headings method [46]. To assist in managing titles across the whole review process (i.e., from initial searches until the step of final inclusion), the Zotero software was used in the present study (v6.0.30; <https://www.zotero.org/>). The researchers involved in each aspect of the development of all the review steps are described in the protocol study [44].

2.2. Eligibility criteria

2.1.1. Inclusion criteria

32 Studies were included (i) when published (even ahead of print) as original research articles, (ii) in scientific peer-reviewed journals, (iii) having its abstract available for screening in the respective databases, (iv) with full-text available – in the English language – for download (i.e. full text download button available for the record in the respective database) and (v) describing aspects related to research ethics with human participants [47] or respective exemption to perform the investigation [48]. Inclusion criteria also included (vi) participants as soccer players and/or human data collected in a football-related environment, (vii) observation and/or experimental protocol including ball kicking (passing or shooting) while (viii) participants used at least one wearable kinematic-based device/system that was (ix) evaluated as concerning its measurement properties (i.e., validity and/or reliability and/or accuracy aspects).

2 2.2.2. Exclusion criteria

Studies were excluded if (i) published in the form of grey literature, (ii) retracted, (iii) investigated only the application/feasibility aspects of wearables, (iv) assessed only movements pertaining to football codes other than ball kicking, (v) explicitly conducted in football codes other than soccer, (vi) observations and/or experimental protocols where a ball was not kicked, (vii) reporting results only concerning ball motion/flight, and (viii) full-texts with no information on the location to which the wearable was attached to the body of participants [44].

2.3. Data extraction

Using custom-prepared Microsoft® Excel spreadsheets (Microsoft Corporation, USA) the following indicators were extracted from the included studies, according to its specific aims [49,50]: (i) validity measures [e.g. correlation coefficient, root mean

27 square difference (RMSD) and area under the receiver operating curve (AUC)]; (ii) reliability measures [e.g. intraclass correlation coefficient (ICC) and coefficient of variation (CV)] and/or accuracy measures (e.g. F1 score, prediction accuracy and percentage of correctly classified activity). For all studies, the main characteristics of methods were also extracted, including wearable (number of sensors, brand of the system/device used, location attached to the body, and acquisition frequency), metrics collected by the wearable, number of participants and sample profile (sex, age, playing level and positional role), experimental protocol (aspects of testing/observation of ball kicking, duration, condition(s) and lower limb considered), form of data analysis, statistical outputs and summary of findings/conclusions.

24 2.4. Methodological quality and risk of bias assessments

19 Here the methodological quality was assessed using the COSMIN checklist or the QUADAS-2 tool, depending on the measurement property addressed by each study. In particular, forms H and B from the COSMIN checklist were adopted to make judgments respectively on the quality of studies that evaluated validity and reliability aspects [51,52]. These studies were rated in each domain of the mentioned tool using a 4-point scale (excellent, good, fair, or poor) [53]. Subsequently, the ratings for each question were converted into values (excellent = 3 points, good = 2 points, fair = 1 point, and poor = 0 points), and then punctuations of all questions were summed for each study. For validity aspects, studies were deemed as having high quality ($\Sigma = 14-18$), moderate quality ($\Sigma = 8-13$), or low quality ($\Sigma = 3-7$). Likewise, for reliability aspects, studies were deemed as having high quality ($\Sigma = 25-33$), moderate quality ($\Sigma = 14-24$) or low quality ($\Sigma = 3-13$). For studies assessing accuracy aspects, the QUADAS-2

tool was adopted [54]. These studies were rated in each domain of the mentioned tool using a 3-point scale (low = 2 points, unclear = 1 point, high = 0 points) and then summed for each study. For accuracy aspects, studies were deemed as having high quality ($\Sigma = 11-14$), moderate quality ($\Sigma = 8-10$) or low quality ($\Sigma = 0-7$).

The risk of bias in results or inferences was determined using the RoBANS tool [55].

Each study was analyzed individually, and rated as presenting a low, high, or unclear risk of bias concerning the selection of participants, confounding variables, measurement of exposure, blinding of outcome assessments, incomplete outcome data, and selective outcome reporting. The RevMan software (v5.3; The Cochrane Collaboration, Denmark) was used to compute graphs of the resulting risk of bias. If any discrepancy existed in the rating between the two evaluators involved - in evaluating methodological quality and risk of bias in included studies - a third (senior) researcher was then consulted until reaching a consensus.

2.5. Evidence synthesis

To provide a synthesis of findings across studies, the level of evidence was classified as (a) strong [consistent findings ($\geq 75\%$ of studies reported results in the same direction) across multiple high-quality studies], (b) moderate (consistent findings across multiple moderate-quality and/or one high-quality study), (c) limited (consistent findings across one moderate-quality and/or only low-quality studies) (d) conflicting ($< 75\%$ of studies reported results in the same direction) or (e) no evidence (none studies found). Evidence gap map was also constructed [44].

3. Results

A total of 676 title entries were initially identified when pooling results of the searches across all databases, in addition to titles manually identified. Following the elimination of duplications and low-relevant studies, the fields of title, abstract and keywords of 80 studies were inspected. This procedure resulted in the exclusion of 44 studies. Finally, after reading the full texts of 36 studies assessed for eligibility and applying all the selection criteria, a total of 12 studies [56–67] addressing the measurement properties of wearable-based systems to evaluate soccer kicking features were included in the qualitative synthesis. Given the heterogeneity in methods observed across included studies, a meta-analysis was not possible in the present review. Eight studies evaluated the respective validity aspects [56,57,61–64,66,67], three evaluated reliability [58,62,63], and three evaluated accuracy [59,60,65]. Figure 1 depicts the frequency of studies included according to the year of publication. Reasons for exclusions in the final eligibility stage included, for example, studies available only as conference proceedings, reporting results of kicking aggregated with other actions, or lacking a statement regarding ethics committee (see Figure 2).

Figure 1. Description of the number of included studies according to the publication year.

Figure 2. PRISMA flow diagram.

3.1. Characteristics of studies included

20

The main aspects of methods in the included studies are summarized in Table 2. The total number of participants was $n = 1011$ taking all studies pooled (median = 11 participants). Seven studies included only men participants (58%) [56,57,59,62–64,66], 4 included both men and women (33%) [58,60,61,65], and in one this information was unclear [67]. Eight studies were conducted with adult samples (67%) [56–59,62–64,66], 2 in youth (17%) [60,61], and 1 using both youth and adult [65]. One study included elite players [62], one both elite and sub-elite [56], and the remainder sub-elite, excepting two studies in which unclear information was provided [64,67].

Table 2. Some characteristics extracted from methods from studies included in the current review.

Reference

Metrics collected

Sex

Age

Level

N

Positional

roles

Tested

Wearable

device/system

Frequency

Experimental protocol

Form of data analysis

Validity results

Reliability results

Accuracy results

Validity

Reliability

Accuracy

Bastiaansen et al. [56]

Hip Load; knee load (derived from joint angular accelerations); and knee extension velocity

Men

Adult

Elite; sub-elite

28

All (pooled)

✓

7 IMUs (MPU-9150, InvenSense, San Jose, California, USA)

500 Hz

5 5-m maximal instep kicks aiming at a full-sized goal without accuracy demands

Data compared across playing levels

MANOVA

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--

Blair et al. [57]

4 Foot speed; pelvis velocity; shank, thigh and knee (angular velocity); shank and pelvis (sagittal angle) at impact; max support-knee extension, min kick-leg knee angle and max hip extension

Men

Adult

Sub-elite

10

--

✓

4 IMUs (MVN Link, Xsens Technologies B.V., Enschede, the Netherlands)

240 Hz

17 5 12-m instep kicks 5 12-m inside kicks 5 20-m instep kicks 5 maximal instep kicks

18 Data compared against 12-camera motion analysis system (T-40 series, Vicon Nexus v2, Oxford, UK).

GLMM; Variances; Error; Studentized residual vs predicted plots

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Burland et al. [58]

Tibial acceleration value, cumulative impact load; total steps; cumulative bone stimulus (number of steps multiplied by the tibial acceleration)

Men; Women

Adult

Sub-elite

10

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✓

21 VICON IMeasureU Blue Trident dual-g sensors (IMeasureU, Auckland, New Zealand)

1600 Hz

3 trials passing the ball forward at a self-selected pace

Data analyzed across three test sessions at least 7–10 days apart

--

ICC

--

Cuperman et al. [59]

Tri-axial accelerations and angular velocities of pelvis, thigh and shank

Men

Adult

Sub-elite

11

--

✓

IMUs (Ivinsense MPU-9150)

500 Hz

28 Football-related activities, including passes, shots, jumps, sprints, among others to simulate an actual football match

Data compared against manually annotated category (activity)

--

--

F1 score Prediction Accuracy

de Vries et al. [60]

Accelerometer data (counts) of the ankle

Men; Women

Youth

Sub-elite

58

--

✓

ActiGraph accelerometers (GT1M/GT3X; ActiGraph, Pensacola, FL)

--

20-min activities including sitting, standing, walking, running, rope skipping, kicking the ball, and cycling

Data compared against research assistant recordings

--

--

%Correctly classified activity; Contingency tables

Duncan et al. [61]

Tri-axial accelerometry data for the ankle

Men; Women

Youth

Sub-elite

20

--

✓

GENEActiv accelerometers (Activinsights, Cambridge)

80 Hz

1 5-min for each activity with 5-min resting: lying supine, standing, running, instep

1 passing a football (size 3 ball, over a distance of 5 m at a cadence of 10 and 20 passes/min) and dribbling

Data correlated with metabolic equivalents; compared amongsts activity types

rho-Spearman; ROC curve AUC

Sensitivity Specificity

--

--

Lewis et al. [62]

Velocity of the foot - or ball release velocity

Men

Adult

Elite

4

All (pooled)

✓

✓

5 IMUs (PlayerMaker™, Tel Aviv, Israel; including two components from MPU-9150,

InvenSense, California, USA)

--

12 kicks in a static ball (6 with each foot) at low, moderate or high subjective intensities with foot region self-selected

Data correlated with joint angular velocity from a high-speed camera system (Quintic

Consultancy Ltd, Sutton Coldfield, UK); Data analyzed within-session for each

subjective intensity

r-Pearson

CV

--

Marris et al. [63]

Ball touches and releases occurrences derived from accelerometer and gyroscope traces

Men

Adult

Sub-elite

12

--

✓

✓

5 IMUs (PlayerMaker™, Tel Aviv, Israel; including two components from MPU-9150, InvenSense, California, USA)

1000 Hz

38 8640 ball touches and 5760 releases, in technical soccer tasks where a given player served the ball to another, considering two pre-determined distances (13.2 and 18.7 m)

5 Data contrasted with manual coding/video (SportsCode Elite, v. 11.2.23, SportsTec, Warriewood, Australia); Data analyzed across 3 codings made by the performance analyst concerning a same specific subset of tasks

Proportion of agreement

CV

--

Steijlen et al. [64]

1

Hip and knee joint angles and angular velocities

Men

Adult

--

1

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✓

1

IMUs ICM-20649 (InvenSense, San Jose, CA)

250 Hz

1

3 trials kicking a ball preceded by a few steps, at three different intensities (50, 80, and 100% of maximum effort)

1

Data compared against and correlated with eight cameras (Vicon V5 cameras, Vicon Motion Systems Ltd., UK)

RMSD

CMC

--

--

Stoeve et al. [65]

Triple-axis linear acceleration and angular velocity

Men; Women

Youth; Adult

Sub-elite

836

--

✓

IMUs (brand not specified)

200 Hz

8424 shots and 24,254 passes taken from 10 sessions in laboratory (controlled exercises) and 10 during training or games (field sessions not following a fixed protocol)

Data compared against labeling made by trained experts using video camera recordings

--

--

F1 score Sensitivity

Wilmes et al. [66]

39 Three-dimensional acceleration, angular velocity, and magnetic field strength

Men

Adult

Sub-elite

11

--

✓

2 IMUs (MPU 9150, Invensense, San Jose, CA, USA)

500 Hz

4 short passes (low intensity), 4 long passes (medium intensity)

4 maximum instep kicks (maximal intensity) all interspersed with about 10 s resting

2 Data compared against and correlated with eight optoelectronic motion cameras

(Vicon V5 cameras, Vicon Motion Systems Ltd., Oxford, UK)

ANOVA RMSD CMC

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Yu et al. [67]

Three-dimensional displacements, acceleration and angular velocity; foot velocity and backwing height

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10

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✓

IMU sensor (ICM-20649, TDK InvenSense MEMS Motion Tracking™ Device)

100 Hz

Instep kicking test

Data compared against "Tracker" using two high-speed cameras positioned in front and side view (brand not specified)

RMSD %Error Bland–Altman plots

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7 N: number of participants; min: minimum; max: maximum; ICC: intraclass correlation coefficient; GLMM: general linear mixed-model; % percentage; RMSD: root mean square difference; CMC: coefficient of multiple correlation; -- represents not applicable, information not reported or unclear.

Two studies reported the inclusion of samples of participants from all playing positions (pooled) [56,62], while the information related to the positional role of participants was unclear in all the remainder studies (83%). Common metrics collected by the wearables included velocity [pelvis [57] and foot (25%; [57,62,67])], acceleration [pelvis [59,66], thigh [59,66], shank [58,59,66], ankle [60,61] and foot (33%; [62,63,65,67])], angular displacement (pelvis, shank [57], hip and knee [64]), angular velocity (pelvis [59,66], hip [64], knee [56,57,64], thigh [57,59,66], shank [57,59,66], ankle [62,63] and foot [65,67]), and angular acceleration of the hip and knee [56].

Number of sensors used in data collections ranged from one sensor [67], two (33%; [58,62,63,65]), four [60], five (42%; [56,59,61,64,66]) to seventeen sensors [57].

Placement locations included waist [61], pelvis (33%; [57,59,64,66]), hip [60], thigh (42%; [56,57,59,64,66]), shank (50%; [56–59,64,66]), ankle (17%; [60,61]) and foot (42%; [57,62,63,65,67]). Approximately one-quarter of studies analyzed preferred limbs [56–58], while half assessed both preferred and non-preferred limbs [59,62–66].

The information related to functional lateralization was unclear in three studies [60,61,67]. In addition, some studies also placed devices on the head, upper arm, forearm, sternum, shoulder, hand [57], wrist [61], and lower back [56].

Wearable devices/systems used in included studies consisted of IMUs MPU-9150 (InvenSense) [56,59,62,63,66], ICM-20649 (InvenSense) [64,67], MVN Link (Xsens Technologies) [57], VICON Blue Trident (IMeasureU) [58], PlayerMaker™ [62,63], and accelerometers GT1M/GT3X (ActiGraph) [60] and GENEActiv (Activinsights) [61]. The information regarding the wearable devices/systems used was unclear in one study as [65]. Acquisition frequencies ranged from 80 Hz [61], 100 Hz [67], 200 Hz [65], 240 Hz [57], 250 Hz [64], 500 Hz [56,59,66], 1000 Hz [63] to 1600 Hz [58]. Two studies presented unclear information relating to acquisition frequency [60,62].

The time of testing across studies varied from 5 minutes [58], 10 minutes [56], and 15 minutes of warming-up, plus the experimental protocol [66]. One study provided 15 minutes of familiarization plus experimental protocol [62]. Three studies provided descriptions of the duration of the protocol, consisting of 5 minutes [61], 20 minutes [60], 35 ± 17 to 73 ± 38 minutes [65]. Unclear information about the total time duration of warm-up and/or experimental protocol was observed in five studies (~42%;

[57,59,63,64,67]), for which information on the composition of the experimental protocol, but not timing, was reported. The description of protocols adopted in all studies as regarding ball kicking action is also presented in the Table 2.

Ball kicking was collected as passing in 8 studies (67%; [58–61,63–66]), and shooting in 7 studies (58%; [56,57,59,64–67]). Unclear information about whether ball kicking was collected like pass or shot was presented in one study [62]. Finally, most studies (92%) used protocols consisting in performing ball kicking as closed skill/constrained tasks [56–64,66,67]. There was only one exception in a study that considered data in both conditions, i.e., closed skill/constrained tasks and also open skill/unconstrained tasks format [65].

3.2. Measurement properties

The main results regarding measurement properties (validity, reliability and accuracy) presented by the wearable kinematic-based data collection systems to evaluate ball kicking in soccer are summarized in Table 3. The table also contains the summary - main conclusions - as per provided by the authors of each individual included study. In general, the validity of wearables was claimed by the authors in 7 out of 8 studies [56,57,62–64,66,67], reliability in 2 out of 3 studies [62,63] and accuracy in 3 out of 3 studies [59,60,65].

Table 3. Results regarding measurement properties extracted from studies included in the current review.

Reference

Wearable device/system

Validity

Reliability

Accuracy

Summary

Concurrent

Discriminative

Crossed

Between-session

Within-session

Intra-unit

Event detection

Bastiaansen et al. [56]

MPU-9150, InvenSense

Knee extension velocity and load $p = 0.02$ $ES = 0.94-0.95$

Hip load $p = 0.97$ $ES = 0.02$

Authors claim the discriminative validity of the wearable for the knee load but not for the hip load

Blair et al. [57]

MVN Link, Xsens Technologies

All metrics collected $p = --$ ES = trivial

Authors claim the overall concurrent validity of the wearable

Burland et al. [58]

IMeasureU Blue Trident dual-g, VICON

Cumulative impact load and step count ICC = 0.58-0.87 $p \leq 0.056$ Cumulative
bone stimulus ICC = 0.95-0.96 $p < 0.001$

Authors indicate lower reliability of the wearable to measure ball kicking as compared
to other soccer actions

Cuperman et al. [59]

Ivensense MPU-9150

CNN + bLSTM model F1 score = 96.67% Accuracy = 98.3% QDA, kNN and
decision tree models Accuracy = 40-90%

Authors claim better accuracy of the wearable using deep learning processing models
as compared to traditional machine learning

de Vries et al. [60]

GT1M/GT3X, ActiGraph

1-axis ANN models Correctly classified activity = 71.4-77.9% 3-axis ANN models Correctly classified activity = 82.1-82.4%

Authors claim better accuracy of the wearable using classification models considering triaxial data as compared to uniaxial

Duncan et al. [61]

GENEActiv, Activinsights

Acc count $\rho = 0.67-0.75$ $p = 0.0001$ AUC = 0.62-0.72 Sensitivity = 59.1-75.3 Specificity = 66.3-68.1

Authors indicate low cross-validity of the wearable output

Lewis et al. [62]

PlayerMaker™ / MPU-9150, InvenSense

Ball release velocity $r^2 = 0.96$ $p = --$

Ball release velocity CV = 3.93-14.35%

14 Authors claim the concurrent validity and reliability of the wearable

Marris et al. [63]

PlayerMaker™ / MPU-9150, InvenSense

Ball touches and releases PA = 95.1-97.6% SE = 0.0-0.1%

31 Ball touches and releases CV = 1.8-2.3% SE = 0.0-0.2%

14 Authors claim the concurrent validity and reliability of the wearable

Steijlen et al. [64]

ICM-20649, InvenSense

Hip and knee angle RMSD = 4-18° CMC = 0.63-0.99 Angular velocity RMSD =

61-103°/s CMC = 0.93-0.99 p = --

Authors claim the concurrent validity of the wearable

Stoeve et al. [65]

brand not specified

CNN model F1 score = 0.887-0.928 Sensitivity = 45-84% SVM model F1 score = 0.648-0.815 Sensitivity = 21-39% LSTM and convLSTM models F1 score = 0.777-0.910 Sensitivity = --

Authors claim the accuracy of the wearable using the CNN processing model but not for the SVM model; deep learning models outperformed machine learning

Wilmes et al. [66]

MPU 9150, Invensense

Hip and knee angle RMSD = 5-8° CMC = 0.96-0.97 Angular velocity RMSD = 78-177°/s CMC = 0.81-0.89 p = --

Authors claim the concurrent validity of the wearable

Yu et al. [67]

ICM-20649, TDK InvenSense

Reconstructed position RMSD = 0.07 m Foot velocity RMSD = 7.47 m/s Error = 4%
Backswing height RMSD = 0.74 m Error = 3%

Authors claim the concurrent validity of the wearable

p = p-value; ES = effect size; ICC: intraclass correlation coefficient; RMSD: root mean square difference; CMC: coefficient of multiple correlation; -- represents information not reported or unclear.

13 3.3. Methodological quality and risk of bias in included studies

Table 4 shows the results of methodological quality assessment for the eight studies that addressed validity aspects. All studies showed moderate quality. Item 3 (sample

size) presented the higher number of studies scoring “poor” (100%) followed by item 6 (38% of studies on this topic lacked correlations or AUC calculations).

Table 4. Ratings of methodological quality from studies that addressed validity aspects.

2 Reference

Item 1

Item 2

Item 3

Item 4

Item 5

Item 6

Item 7

Rating

6 Bastiaansen et al. [56]

Good

Fair

Poor

Fair

Excellent

Excellent

NA

Moderate

6

Blair et al. [57]

Good

Fair

Poor

Excellent

Excellent

Poor

NA

Moderate

Duncan et al. [61]

Good

Fair

Poor

Fair

Excellent

Excellent

Excellent

Moderate

Lewis et al. [62]

Excellent

Fair

Poor

Excellent

11

Excellent

Excellent

NA

Moderate

6

Marris et al. [63]

Good

Fair

Poor

Excellent

Excellent

Poor

NA

Moderate

6

Steijlen et al. [64]

Good

Fair

Poor

Excellent

Excellent

Excellent

NA

Moderate

Wilmes et al. [66]

Good

11 Fair

Poor

Excellent

Excellent

Excellent

NA

Moderate

Yu et al. [67]

Good

Fair

Poor

Good

Excellent

Poor

NA

Moderate

Items from the COSMIN checklist (form H); NA: not applicable.

12 Table 5 shows the results of methodological quality assessment for the three studies that addressed reliability aspects. Once again, all studies showed moderate quality. Item 3 (sample size) presented the higher number of studies scoring “poor”, followed by item 11 (67% of studies on this topic lacked ICC calculations).

Table 5. Ratings of methodological quality from studies that addressed reliability aspects.

2 Reference

Item 1

Item 2

Item 3

Item 4

Item 5

Item 6

Item 7

Item 8

Item 9

Item 10

Item 11

Rating

Burland et al. [58]

Good

Fair

Poor

35 Excellent

Excellent

Excellent

Good

Excellent

Good

Fair

Excellent

Moderate

Lewis et al. [62]

23

Excellent

Fair

Poor

Excellent

Good

Fair

Good

Fair

Good

Fair

Poor

Moderate

Marris et al. [63]

26

Good

Fair

Poor

26

Excellent

Good

Fair

Good

Fair

Good

Fair

Poor

Moderate

Items from the COSMIN checklist (form B); Items 12-14 did not apply to studies included in the present review.

12

Table 6 shows the results of methodological quality assessment for the three studies that addressed accuracy aspects. Two studies had moderate methodological quality while one study showed low methodological quality (33%). Item A from the domain 1 (patient selection) showed the high number of studies rated with the poorest score (100% with a high risk of bias relating to the selection of participants).

1

Table 6. Ratings of methodological quality from studies that addressed accuracy aspects.

Reference

1

Domain 1

1

Domain 2

Domain 3

Domain 4

Rating

15

Item A

Item B

Item A

Item B

Item A

Item B

Item A

8

Cuperman et al. [59]

High

Unclear

Low

Unclear

Unclear

Unclear

Unclear

Low

de Vries et al. [60]

High

Unclear

Low

Low

Unclear

Low

Unclear

Moderate

Stoeve et al. [65]

High

Low

Low

Low

Unclear

Low

Unclear

Moderate

Items from the QUADAS-2 tool.

29 Figures 3 and 4 contain, respectively, the results of risk of bias for individual studies and a summary of results for all studies pooled. The item selection of participants

presented a higher number of studies rated as high risk (17%). The item blinding of outcome assessment showed the higher number of studies rated as unclear risk (75%).

9 Figure 3. Judgments made about each risk of bias item for each included study.

Figure 4. Risk of bias for each item as percentages across all included studies.

3.4. Summary of evidence

Figure 6 depicts the interaction between measurement properties and kinematic data collected by wearables in studies included. Open circles are the number of studies. Thresholds for qualitative synthesis were applied according to described previously (section 2.5). Regardless of the outcome variable, taking into account the wearable devices/systems and the measurement properties (Figure 7), the MPU-9150 (InvenSense) showed moderate evidence on concurrent validity across studies [62,63,66], limited evidence on discriminative validity [56], within-session reliability [62], intra-unit reliability [63], and event detection accuracy [59] and no evidence on between-session reliability. The ICM-20649 (InvenSense) showed moderate evidence on concurrent validity across studies [64,67] and no evidence on the remainder of measurement properties. The PlayerMaker™ showed moderate evidence on concurrent validity across studies [62,63], limited evidence on within-session reliability

[62], intra-unit reliability [63], and no evidence for the remainder of measurement properties. All the other devices/systems (MVN Link-Xsens Technologies [57], VICON Blue Trident-IMeasureU [58], GT1M/GT3X-ActiGraph [60] and GENEActiv-Activinsights [61]) showed limited-to-no evidence on the measurement properties. Finally, limited-to-no evidence was also identified across studies when considering wearable devices/systems, measurement properties and specific outcome variables.

Figure 6. Interaction between the measurement properties tested and kinematic data collected by the wearables.

Open circles represent the number of studies. vel: velocity; acc: acceleration; ang: angular; disp: displacement.

Figure 7. Evidence gap map regarding the measurement properties tested and the wearable devices/systems used.

4. Discussion

1 The present systematic review aimed to synthesize the evidence on the measurement properties (i.e., validity, reliability, and/or accuracy) of wearable kinematic-based systems used for evaluating ball kicking in soccer. While a meta-analysis was not viable in the present investigation due to variations in various aspects of methods across the included studies and the generally reduced number of available published studies on the subject, the best evidence synthesis and gap map methods allowed us to draw some inferences. The main findings revealed moderate evidence supporting the concurrent validity of wearable systems, including the (i) MPU-9150, (ii) ICM-20649 - both i and ii pertaining to InvenSense (San Jose, California, USA) - and (iii) PlayerMaker™ (Tel Aviv, Israel), for soccer kicking analysis in controlled settings. However, evidence on between-session reliability and accuracy remains limited, particularly in real-game scenarios. The current study is a revised and expanded version of a previous conference paper [68].

The studies included predominantly focused on the validity of wearable systems, with a significant proportion showing its concurrent validity for different measures (e.g., joint angles, velocity, and acceleration). The moderate evidence supporting the concurrent validity of wearable devices MPU-9150, ICM-20649, and PlayerMaker™ in controlled environments [62–64,67] suggests a great capability for these wearables to measure

kinematic variables with a degree of accuracy that aligns with the gold-standard instruments for the same purpose. Regarding other wearables, such as the MVN Link system, Blair et al. [57] suggested that the MVN Link system has concurrent validity compared to a high-standard motion analysis system. However, the high error levels observed in faster kicking attempts indicate that while the system can detect movements, the precision of this system might be velocity-dependent. Moreover, limited evidence was found for devices like GT1M/GT3X and GENEActiv. Their use in assessing kicking kinematics was less straightforward, showing moderate correlations for certain activities but not specifically highlighting their effectiveness for detailed kinematic kicking analysis [61]. The low cross-validity (i.e., for the GENEActiv) indicates that devices might be better suited for general activity recognition rather than precise kinematic measurements in particular movements or tasks. Most of these devices were not specifically designed for the high-speed, high-impact nature of soccer kicking, which may explain the limited evidence in kicking kinematic analysis.

The capability for these wearables to measure kinematic variables with a degree of accuracy that aligns with the gold-standard instruments is crucial as it benchmarks the actual technology used against established methods, providing a basis for further exploration into their practical utility in sporting settings [69]. However, the inherent variability in soccer kicking velocity and accuracy [43,70–74] requires wearables that measure and interpret these actions considering its context. This fact is not uniquely challenging to soccer; similar demands for contextual data interpretation are also needed in other sports where precision and variability in movement are paramount (e.g. the tennis serves [75]). Furthermore, the distortion of time-series data due to the

1 impact of the foot with the ball also complicates this scenario of contextual factors [40,41]. Indeed, the variability in validity outcomes of the included studies in the present systematic review exposes the complexity of collecting biomechanical data in real-world sports settings [14,30,76].

The still limited evidence on reliability (e.g., between-session) and the event detection accuracy showed an important gap in the practical application of the wearable technologies in the context of soccer kicking assessment. This is critical as reliability over time and across different conditions is essential for wearables to be integrated effectively into the training process to improve decision-making. Another systematic review that addressed the use of IMUs in volleyball also identified reliability results that were worse than validity ones [77]. The limited between-session reliability and accuracy in real-game scenarios found in the present systematic review might be attributed to (i) the possible negative results from (unpublished) research carried out [78], (ii) on the occasion that (i) is true then there might be a need to improve existing data/equipment capture/processing methods and/or (iii) differences in sensor placement, in the number of sensors used, or the specific measures being measured (e.g., velocity, acceleration). Burland et al. [58] explored the reliability of the VICON Blue Trident (IMeasureU) system, finding moderate to high ICC values during kicking actions. However, the lower reliability for ball kicking compared to other actions assessed (i.e., locomotion tasks without ball handling) suggests that the nature of kicking might introduce variability that affects the device's consistency. This could be due to the placement of sensors or the sensitivity to rapid changes in acceleration. Regardless of the measurement property, replication studies are encouraged using an

adequate/sufficient number of participants [79] given that the included studies of the present systematic review showed in general low sample sizes. The same problem of a small number of participants across literature studies was identified in a systematic review that covered the topic of wearables in basketball [38].

Studies utilizing foot-mounted sensors like the PlayerMaker™ system have shown potential, yet the generalizability of these findings to other wearable configurations or all player positions remains uncertain. Specifically, the placement of sensors may directly affect data accuracy [80]. Foot-mounted sensors might excel in capturing kicking dynamics in controlled settings. Still, they might not generalize to real-world settings [81], such as training context, where impacts and other inter-player contacts are very likely to occur. Thus, here the presence of potential biases arising from experimental (e.g. controlled) conditions should be not overlooked. Using observations from well-defined ball kicking as closed skill/constrained tasks would possibly favors one outcome over others. Also, the need for regular calibration or updates to software algorithms to account for new data or different playing conditions is often overlooked, and reliability can be negatively affected [39]. Furthermore, as players fatigue, their biomechanics and outcomes change [82,83], potentially leading to different between-session data outputs from wearables [84]. This aspect of the soccer training context may explain the still limited evidence on the reliability and accuracy of data over multiple sessions. Moreover, accuracy in event detection, particularly for kicking, was not explicitly detailed for many of these devices. Notwithstanding, soccer kicking performance (e.g. ball release velocity) has been position-dependent in either youth/adult or men/women players [85–87]. In addition, in-game situations like ground

duels could potentially create challenges for the signal processing of wearables in soccer context, and also vary according to playing position [88,89]. Thus, future analysis of measurement properties in wearables should consider present results also separated by playing position. It is also advisable that the metrics included be justified in relation to their actual practical meaningfulness (e.g. importance to the monitoring of performance of the kicking skill/overall player performance, age-related development and/or injury risk mitigation).

The present systematic review has inherent limitations. Firstly, our focus was narrowed to the validity, reliability, and accuracy of wearable devices in soccer kicking actions, which might not capture the full capabilities of wearable technology applications in soccer or other sports. Although this seems the case also in other team sports (e.g. handball [90]), it is also necessary to recognise that in the analysis (i.e., qualitative synthesis) considering wearable devices/systems, measurement properties and specific outcome variables, limited to no evidence was verified in the current literature. Another significant limitation is the demographic bias, where there was a predominance of men and adult participants in included studies, thereby limiting the generalizability of our findings across the broader populations. Using a traditional approach to systematically review the literature (e.g., excluding conference proceedings [91–98]) may have led to the overlooking of potentially worthwhile scientific findings in the synthesis presented. Our review's lack of longitudinal studies highlights a gap in understanding how these technologies perform over time. It would be beneficial for future studies to adopt a broader inclusion criterion, encompassing studies that include other football codes to ensure that wearable technology's benefits

are applicable. As for example, another potential limitation of methods in the current review is that - in an attempt to collate specific evidence for the team sport of soccer - the realization of studies explicitly conducted in football codes other than soccer was established as an exclusion criterion. Also, ball kicking outcomes are age-dependent [99–102]. In studies regarding the measurement property accuracy, only one used a sample of exclusively senior participants, while the other two used solely youth or mixed samples (adult and senior pooled). Extrapolating the measurement properties of studies with youth participants to seniors requires caution, and the opposite, too. The same thought can be derived as regarding competitive standards; results encountered in the non-elite levels may not be interchangeable with the elite, due to the distinct kicking outputs according to playing standards [103–105]. In the present review, only two studies investigated the measurement properties of wearables in elite players, and their use in practice has become increasingly widespread in recent years among professional clubs. Moreover, standardization of testing and calibration protocols for these devices could improve the consistency and comparability of the outcomes (e.g., using recommendations from the International Society of Biomechanics [106]). Finally, there is a need to test and reporting aspects related to the robustness of sensor solutions, its adaptation to the player body segments and resilience levels to cope with impacts and other inter-player contacts. Longitudinal research also considering the duration of official matches and training sessions should be prioritized to assess the long-term reliability and utility of wearable data.

5. Conclusions

1 From the present systematic review with best evidence synthesis and evidence gap map methods, it is possible to conclude that there is a knowledge base that may

1 support implementation of wearables to assess ball kicking in practice. The wearable

1 devices/systems that have so far the highest level of evidence - moderate - on the validity (i.e., concurrent) across existing literature studies are the MPU-9150 (InvenSense), ICM-20649 (InvenSense) and PlayerMaker™ (Tel Aviv, Israel). In contrast, limited-to-no evidence is noted regardless of the wearable devices/systems considered regarding both reliability (e.g., between-session) and accuracy (event detection) aspects. Also, conclusions are applicable to a greater extent to men adult players. Future research should further evaluate the measurement properties of wearables to attempt to reach a strong evidence level as regarding their performance in assessing ball kicking in soccer, mainly considering the inclusion of a sufficient number of players, underrepresented populations (e.g. female and youth players) and data collection approaches during actual training sessions and official matches.